

ESTIMATE THE MARKETING COST, MARGIN, EFFICIENCY, PRODUCERS SHARES IN CONSUMERS RUPEE AND MARKETING CHANNELS OF GARLIC, IN RATLAM DISTRICT OF MADHYA PRADESH.

¹.Gourav Chouhan, ² Dr. Sanjay Kumar

1. P.G. student MBA (Agribusiness), Department of Agriculture Economics, Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Science, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

2. Assistant Professor, Department of Agriculture Economics, Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Science, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the various channels involved in marketing garlic in Ratlam district of Madhya Pradesh, India, and evaluate the marketing efficiency, market margin, marketing cost, and producers' shares in the consumer's rupee. Ratlam district is renowned for its garlic production and serves as a significant market for garlic trading. By examining the marketing channels, we can gain insights into the distribution patterns and the roles played by different intermediaries in connecting garlic producers with consumers. Additionally, evaluating marketing efficiency shed light on the effectiveness of these channels in terms of minimizing wastage, reducing transaction costs, and ensuring timely delivery of garlic to the consumers. The assessment of market margins provide an understanding of the profit margins earned by each intermediary in the marketing chain, highlighting areas of potential price exploitation or market inefficiencies. Moreover, the analysis of marketing costs enable us to quantify the expenses incurred by different stakeholders, including transportation, storage, packaging, and marketing services. Lastly, determining the producers' shares in the consumer's rupee assesses the income distribution among garlic growers relative to the final retail price paid by consumers. The findings of this study is contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the garlic marketing system in Ratlam district and provide insights for enhancing the efficiency and profitability of this important agricultural value chain.

Keywords: Marketing efficiency, market margin, marketing cost, producers' shares, Ratlam.

Introduction

Garlic (*Allium sativum*), a widely consumed and economically significant agricultural product, is marketed through a complex network of channels worldwide. This research focuses on analysing the various channels involved in marketing garlic in Ratlam district, located in Madhya Pradesh, India. The global demand for garlic has been steadily increasing due to its culinary versatility and perceived health benefits. This demand has led to a dynamic international market with numerous stakeholders, including producers, exporters, importers, wholesalers, and retailers. Understanding the global dynamics of garlic marketing provides valuable insights into the factors that influence local markets and opens avenues for Ratlam district to tap into international demand. At the state level, Madhya Pradesh has emerged as a leading garlic producer in India, benefiting from favourable agro-climatic conditions. Ratlam district, known for its extensive garlic production, plays a crucial role in aggregating garlic from neighboring regions and connecting it to both local and external consumers. By analysing the marketing channels in Ratlam district, this study aims to assess the efficiency of these channels in terms of minimizing losses, optimizing resource utilization, and ensuring timely availability of garlic to consumers. Furthermore, evaluating market margins will shed light on the profit distribution among intermediaries, uncovering potential areas of price exploitation or market inefficiencies. The analysis of marketing costs will provide insights into the expenses incurred by stakeholders, including transportation, storage, packaging, and marketing services. Determining the producers' shares in the consumer's rupee will assess the income distribution among garlic growers relative to the final retail price paid by consumers. The findings of this research will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the garlic marketing system in Ratlam district, providing insights to enhance efficiency and profitability in this important agricultural value chain.

Research Methodology**Size of Samples:**

DISTRICT	Ratlam
BLOCK	Ratlam
VILLAGES	Dharad, Ambodiya & Bilpank.
SMALL SIZE (Up to 2 Ha)	25
MEDIUM SIZE (2 to 10 Ha)	25
LARGE SIZE (> 10Ha)	25
Total	75

Sampling technique:

A multistage stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select the block, villages and the respondents, market and different functionaries involved in garlic marketing in Ratlam district. The details of the sampling techniques at various stages are given as under.

(i) Selection of block:

A list of all the development blocks of district Ratlam was prepared out of these blocks, one development block, Ratlam was selected having highest area under garlic cultivation.

(ii) Selection of the villages:

A list of all the villages growing garlic, falling under selected block was prepared and cluster of three villages were selected.

(iii) Selection of farmers:

From each of the selected village, a list of garlic growers was prepared in ascending order, according to the size of their holding. Stratified random sampling procedure was adopted for the selection of ultimate sampling unit of garlic producers from selected three villages. The garlic producing farmers 22 were then categorized as small (>2 ha.), medium (2 to 10 ha.) and large (above 10 ha.), based on land holding size of the farmers, 25 farmers from each selected village were selected randomly among three size groups. All the sample garlic producers were sold their produce through the forwarding agent in the wholesale market. The actual marketing cost incurred by the sample garlic producers through different channels was considered. The tabular method and percentage analysis were carried out to examine costs, margins and price spread in Ratlam vegetable mandi. The relevant information regarding the marketing of garlic was obtained from these selected market intermediaries by interviewing personally with the help of pretested schedules. The primary data on the relevant, aspects specified in objectives were collected from the sample farmers for the reference year 2020-21 survey method.

Table 1: Number of villages and selected farmers of Ratlam block.

Name of selected villages	Number Of families selected			Total
	Small (1-2 ha.)	Medium (2-10 ha.)	Large (Above 10ha.)	
Dharad	8	8	9	25
Ambodiya	9	8	8	25
Bilpank	8	9	8	25

Marketing efficiency

Acharya's Formula (Acharya and Agrawal, 2001) was used for estimating the marketing efficiency which is given as:

$$\text{Marketing Efficiency} = \frac{FP}{(MC+MM)}$$

Where,

FP = Price received by the farmer

MC = Total Marketing Cost

MM = Net Market Margins.

Marketing Margin

Marketing Margin of middleman calculated as the difference between the total payments (marketing cost + purchase price) and receipts (sale price) of the middlemen and calculated as follows.

$$A_{mi} = P_{Ri} - (P_{pi} + C_{mi})$$

Where,

A_{mi} = Absolute margin of middlemen

P_{Ri} = Total value of receipts per unit (sale price)

P_{pi} = Purchase value of goods per unit

C_{mi} = Cost incurred on marketing per unit

GMM (Rs) = Consumer's price – Producers

Marketing Costs

different channels involved in marketing garlic in study area.

Identified marketing channels of Garlic area under study.

Channel –I	Producer to consumer
Channel –II	Producer to retailer to consumer
Channel –III	Producer to wholesaler to retailer to Consumer

The total cost, incurred on marketing by the garlic growers and various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of the commodity till the commodity reaches to the ultimate consumer was calculated as:

$$TC_m = C + \sum_{i=1}^n MC_i$$

Where,

TC_m = Total cost of persimmon marketing,

C_g = Cost paid by the grower in the marketing of his produce

MC_i = Marketing costs incurred by i^{th} middleman.

Producer's share in consumer's rupee:

It is the ratio of price received by the farmer to the retail price. It was calculated by using the formula:

$$PS = \frac{PF}{RP} \times 100$$

Where,

PS = Producer's share in consumer's rupee

PF = Farmer's price (i.e. price received by the farmer/ producer per unit of output)

RP = Retail price (consumer's price) per unit of output

MM = Total marketing margins

Table: 2 marketing agencies in garlic marketing across identical. (Percentage)

S. No.	Particulars	Channel- I	Channel-II	Channel-III
1	Producer's share	98.68	93.63	90.79
2	Producer's cost	1.31	1.24	6.17
3	Wholesaler's shares	-	2.62	-
4	Wholesaler's cost	-	2.49	-
5	Retailer's share	-	-	1.81
6	Retailer's cost	-	-	1.21
	(Rs./q)	3800 (100)	4005 (100)	4130 (100)

Fig.1: Different marketing agencies in garlic marketing across identical.

Different marketing agencies in garlic marketing across identical
The efficiency of marketing denoted here that when there was no functionalities between the interaction of producer and consumer the market efficiency was higher which tend to decline as per increase of number of marketing functionalities and services rendered by them including their respective margin. The marketing efficiency also

indicates that if there is creation of utility in a consumer's good in the form of place, time, and form utility its higher degree may be more appreciable as it converted the raw material nearly to more usable form for consumer but without increasing such utilities the expansion of cost and margins of market agencies incurred in the trading of commodities will definitely reduce the efficiency of that commodity in market.

Table :3 Comparison of different marketing channels in garlic Marketing

S. No.	Particulars	Value of the good (Rs/ha)	Total marketing cost (Rs)	Total margin (Rs.)	Final value of the good (Rs/q)
1	Channel –I	3750	50	-	3800
2	Channel –II	3750	50	105	4005
3	Channel –III	3750	200	180	4130

Post harvest technique prevalence in study area:

In the case of garlic crop there was no post harvest technique followed at producer's level except drying of bulb for a time being and grading of that as per their convenience and removing of dry roots of the bulbs. A few producers having their own store or godown keep this

commodity for a time being and observe the waiting period for better price in future. During the survey period respondents taken into account had no such facilities therefore, study in this respect was not further extended

Table :4 Comparison of different marketing channels in garlic marketing.

S.No.	Particulars	Channel 1
1	Total cost Marketing	50
2	Total margin (middleman)	-
3	Total price spread	1.31%
4	Producer share consumer rupees	98.68%
5	Marketing efficiency	98.69

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Conclusion

The analysis of the different marketing channels involved in garlic marketing in the study area reveals interesting insights. Channel I, which involves direct interaction between the producer and the consumer, demonstrates the highest producer's share of 98.68% in the consumer's rupee. However, as we move towards Channel II and Channel III, where intermediaries like retailers and wholesalers are involved, the producer's share decreases to 93.63% and 90.79% respectively. This decline in the producer's share is accompanied by an increase in marketing costs and margins for the intermediaries. The comparison of different marketing channels also highlights the impact on the final value of the garlic. Channel III, with the involvement of wholesalers and retailers, leads to the highest final value of the garlic at Rs. 4130 per quintal, whereas Channel I, with direct producer-to-consumer interaction, has the lowest final value at Rs. 3800 per quintal. The efficiency of the marketing channels is also evaluated based on the total cost of marketing, total margin earned by middlemen, price spread, producer's share in consumer rupees, and overall marketing efficiency. Channel I exhibits the highest marketing efficiency of 98.69%, followed by Channel II with 93.64%, and Channel III with 90.79%. These findings suggest that the efficiency of the marketing system declines as the number of intermediaries and their associated costs and margins increase.

In conclusion, the data highlights the impact of different marketing channels on the distribution of shares, costs, margins, and efficiency in garlic marketing. Direct producer-to-consumer interaction results in higher producer's shares and greater marketing efficiency. However, as intermediaries such as wholesalers and retailers enter the picture, the producer's share decreases, and marketing costs and margins increase. Understanding these dynamics is essential for optimizing marketing strategies, reducing costs, and ensuring fair returns for garlic producers in the study area.

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